

07 On Discrete Euclidean Space

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The paper is the seventh post of the blog “Discrete Euclidean Space” at <https://www.conceptualframeworks.org>. The post is about some consequences of the scalar mechanism of the units of the structure of discrete space.

The scalar mechanism

The shape of every unit of discrete space is determined by the property that is termed “scalar mechanism”. An internal spherical shape forming mechanism that is responsible for the way observable reality is displayed (see **01** and **05**).

All the units of discrete space have identical basic properties and the volume of the universe is totally filled with the units of discrete space. Actually, the universe is discrete space. The consequence is that all the units change their shape synchronously and continuous because there exists no geometrical symmetry inside every unit and no geometrical symmetry in the universe as a whole (the universe reflects the properties of the units).

Because of the mutual synchronous change of the shapes of every unit the amount of topological deformation of each unit is quantized (fixed amounts of deformed volume of every unit). Now there raises a problem.

figure 1

Suppose the total deformation of a unit is n quanta, fixed amounts of topological deformation. But there is an adjacent unit and its total deformation is $n + 120$ quanta. A higher amount of deformation creates dominant vectors in relation to the other vectors around and to decrease its deformation – trying to become a full scalar – the unit has to

transfer at least 119 quanta during $119 t_c$ (constant of time) to obtain nearly the same amount of average deformation like all the other units around.

If I try to imagine this process of reducing topological deformation by the push force of the scalar mechanism it seems to be reasonable that the highest deformed unit can transfer its surplus of topological deformation to the units around. Just because of the dominant scalar vectors. But is it true?

Figure 1 shows the imaginary symmetrical unit, inclusive the scalar vectors to the points of contact with the other scalars around (not drawn). If I make a horizontal cross section I get the “boundary shape” of figure 2.

figure 2

Every unit has 6 adjacent units, so there are 3 adjacent units “above” the cross-section and 3 adjacent units “below” the cross-section (figure 2, **05**). Suppose the 6 faces of the unit in figure 2 represent ΔV_{output} , like the red arrows in figure 2, **04**). But the output deformation in a face of a unit is the input deformation of the adjacent unit. Figure 2 shows that we cannot hypothesize about adjacent units that differ with a huge amount of topological deformation from each other. Because topological deformation is deformation, no matter if it is thought to be positive or negative.

If the 6 faces of the unit in the centre of figure 2 are positive, the other 6 faces are negative (ΔV_{input}). That means

that above and under the cross-section of figure 2 the blue coloured scalar vectors of the adjacent units must have the opposite direction. I have visualized the consequence with the help of the image in figure 3. The green arrows represent the topological deformation of ΔV_{output} and the red arrows ΔV_{input} .

figure 3

It is obvious that the configuration in figure 3 cannot exist without a large number of involved quite deformed units around to create the inevitable loop. Because every unit shares all its faces with the 12 adjacent units around.

Scalar vectors can be added and subtracted and that's why a large amount of units can concentrate topological deformation to a limited number of units in the centre of the involved units, like figure 4 (figure 3, 03).

figure 4

The schematic cross section in figure 5 is nearly identical to figure 2 but now the deformation is part of a simple circular loop. The units near the boundary of the loop don't show a high deformation because all the "small" scalar vectors of the units around ($n \times +1$) are added together. In other words, the creation of a particle is a process that concentrates quanta that is caused by the "push force" of the scalar mechanism of every unit of discrete space.

The transfer of one quantum has a duration of $1 t_c$ (constant of time). The linear velocity is the constant speed of light and the consequence is that spatial configurations like the

creation of a rest mass carrying particle with the help of a roughly closed loop of topological deformation will take a certain amount of time. Thus every distinct spatial configuration of topological deformation will have a specific duration – and needs specific conditions – to be created. A duration that is determined by the number of involved units, the trajectory of each transferred quantum of deformation and the total number of transferred quanta. And – last but not least – the local surplus of topological deformation that can be transferred. Because the imaginary unit in figure 1 has a symmetrical shape that will pass on fixed amounts of topological deformation but isn't the source of a local surplus of deformation.

figure 5

Figure 5 shows that the magnitude of the scalar vectors don't determine the local configuration. It is the mutual relation between the involved number of units that is responsible for the result because every unit has the same basic properties (invariant volume and scalar mechanism).

The loop between ΔV_{output} and ΔV_{input} is observable at every scale size in our universe. The spin of a particle, the electron of an atom, the rotation of stars, the orbit of a planet, the rotation of a galaxy, etc. Actually, the classical law of conservation of energy – an insight that was amplified by the development of the steam engine – is the expression of the equivalence between ΔV_{output} and ΔV_{input} .

The transformation of the configuration of the left image into the right image of figure 4 isn't possible if there is much disturbance within the volume. A hypothesis that is confirmed at the macroscopic scale because hot clouds of gasses and dust don't transform into concentrations of matter that will become a brown dwarf or a star.

At the microscopic scale we cannot observe the creation of matter if the required energy isn't already concentrated in the form of a high energy electromagnetic wave. That is

why it is more practical to simulate the creation of a particle with the help of a model that represents the basic properties of discrete space with the help of a computer. A solution that can be simplified if we “blow up” the fixed amount of topological deformation. It reduces the number of “directly” involved units. “Directly” in the sense that the configuration can transform geometrically into a concentration of topological deformation that shows the properties of a rest mass carrying particle.

where in the universe – see figure 7 – has to facilitate the creation of energy concentrations that will result in the creation of matter. However, the volume of every unit of discrete space is invariant and all the units deform their shape synchronous with all the other units. A continuous transformation of mutual relations that is not only deterministic but shows all the qualifications of a self generating fractal. A concept we don’t like in phenomenological physics.

Figure 6 shows the cross section of a realistic deformation of the joint face of 2 units. I have drawn the appearance of the face of the right unit too. The dark blue colour “symbolises” the involved volume of the deformable parts of both adjacent units.

figure 6

If the volume of the deformable part – in physics termed *electric field* – of the right unit increases the inscribed sphere – the scalar – of the left unit, it will decrease its radius. The result is a local decreased scalar within the flat Higgs field. However ΔV_{output} is equal to ΔV_{input} thus the higher the local deformation the more units are involved in a direct way, seen with the help of the phenomenological point of view.

figure 7

Unfortunately our universe is non-local (**04**). The consequence is that the change of all the scalar vectors every-

